

NEWSLETTER

January 2026

VALIAS is an Innovative Action funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101131441 (HORIZON-MSCA-2020-SE-01).

The project's main objective is to protect marine ecosystems from invasive alien species (IAS) by creating new valuable chains from their underexploited biomass feedstock.

Advanced biotechnological processes are developed and optimized to transform IAS biomass into valuable products, contributing to a circular economy while protecting marine ecosystems.

The project consortium is consisting of 8 partners from 5 countries.

The project officially began in January 2024 and its duration is 48 months.

<https://valias.eu/>

6 Work Packages

Focusing on IAS sustainable harvesting techniques and innovative biomass utilization processes. VALIAS covers everything from product development to stakeholder engagement, ensuring an efficient workflow and strong collaboration among our partners.

A few words from the Project Coordinator

It is a great pleasure to address you as the new Coordinator of the VALIAS Project, representing Prinsus, the spin-off company of the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA).

VALIAS stands at the forefront of innovation by transforming the challenge of invasive alien species (IAS) into an opportunity for sustainable development. Through strong collaboration among our consortium partners from five European countries, the project continues to advance nature-based solutions that support marine biodiversity, circular bioeconomy principles, and the creation of high-value products for the food, feed, cosmetics, and pharmaceutical sectors.

A key strength of VALIAS lies in its people. With 318 secondment months planned, the project will provide training to at least 30 researchers, fostering excellence in IAS management, sustainable resource utilization, and innovative product development. These efforts will significantly contribute to knowledge exchange between academia and industry while promoting long-term ecosystem sustainability.

In the coming months, VALIAS will organize workshops and knowledge-sharing events to disseminate our results and engage with a wider audience. I warmly invite all stakeholders to follow our progress and participate in these activities as we work together to protect marine ecosystems and build new value chains from invasive species.

I look forward to collaborating closely with all partners and stakeholders to ensure the successful implementation of the VALIAS Project.

Professor Magdalini (Magda) Krokida
Project Coordinator – VALIAS
Prinsus Spin-off Company, NTUA

Partners

1. Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR)

Coordinator of the VALIAS project, responsible for marine biodiversity research and activities related to the management of marine invasive alien species (IAS). The institution offers expertise in population management and the valorization of marine resources.

<https://www.hcmr.gr>

2. PRINSUS

Dissemination manager for the project, with expertise in communication, recovery of valuable compounds from marine IAS and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of processes and products. PRINSUS is also responsible for encapsulation and sustainability assessments.

<https://prinsus.eu>

3. Agriculture and Food Development Authority (TEAGASC)

A partner specializing in agricultural research and food development. TEAGASC is responsible for developing commercially viable products from IAS, including functional food, cosmetics and novel fish feed. They also evaluate these products for safety and commercial potential.

<https://www.teagasc.ie/>

4. University of Salento (UNILE)

Research partner specializing in species selection. UNILE works on mapping additional IAS species, collecting literature data and establishing criteria for species selection. They contribute significantly to the scientific foundation of the project.

<https://www.unisalento.it/>

5. NUEVO

Technical partner focusing on product quality assessment. NUEVO evaluates the nutritional value, quality, and performance of new aquafeed formulations from IAS. They play a key role in ensuring that the final products meet industry standards.

<https://nuevo-group.com/>

6. European University Cyprus (EUC)

Regulatory and safety partner. EUC conducts safety testing and regulatory compliance for IAS-derived products. They focus on pre-clinical safety studies and ensure that the products meet European legal standards.

<https://euc.ac.cy/en/>

7. Bantry Marine Research Station (BMRS)

Marine research specialists. BMRS works on selecting species of interest, conducting literature reviews, and performing safety tests on VALIAS ingredients. They also support environmental assessments for the project's activities.

<https://www.bmrs.ie/>

8. Physiopharma

Cosmetic development partner. Physiopharma focuses on creating anti-aging cosmetic products from IAS-derived bioactive substances. They conduct market studies, evaluate skin health benefits and assess product formulations.

<https://physiopharma.bg/>

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New Partners

9. Mersea Consulting

Strategic development, consultancy supporting innovation and sustainability specialists. With strong experience in research, their work helps create practical outcomes that positively affect everyday life. Their contributions help make communities healthier, smarter, and more sustainable.

<https://mersea.org/>

10. CENTIV GmbH

Engineering and food research specialists. Their work focuses on key global challenges such as sustainable food systems, alternative proteins, and circular economy initiatives-supporting food security and waste reduction.

<http://www.centiv.de/>

INSPIRE SCIENCE
EMPOWERING TOMORROW'S INNOVATORS

11. INSPIRE SCIENCE SRL

A partner sharing the same vision for brighter future.INSPIRE SCIENCE SRL is an organization of true pioneers, dedicated to sparking curiosity and driving meaningful progress through the world of discovery. They are nurturing the young minds who will eventually solve the world's most pressing global challenges.

<https://inspirescience.net/>

VAIAS participating Countries

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Secondments ✈✈✈✈✈

318 Secondment months in 8 countries

As of January 31st 2026, 48 secondments with total duration of 93 months have been completed from 37 researchers (30%).

"Participating in the VALIAS secondment program was an incredible milestone for my professional development. My time at the PRINSUS project in Athens allowed me to dive deep into advanced laboratory techniques and collaborate with a brilliant team in a new environment. Beyond the technical skills I gained, the experience of working in Greece was truly amazing. It broadened my perspective and enhanced my career trajectory. I am sincerely grateful to the VALIAS team for providing me with such a transformative and life-changing opportunity. Rabel Suchintita Das Teagasc who joined us from Teagasc, Ireland.

"My special thanks to the PRINSUS team that allowed me to expand my scientific skills, collaborate with inspiring researchers, and immerse myself in a new environment. I'm truly grateful for the support I received and for the opportunity to contribute to such meaningful work. It has had a very positive impact on my career, and it's an experience I will always cherish. This secondment has been a special and enriching experience for my career." Gaoya Dong, who joined us from Teagasc, Ireland

"My secondment at Prinsus in Athens was an extraordinary experience that has significantly impacted my professional journey. Being able to move from Teagasc to

the laboratory in Greece allowed me to broaden my technical horizons and work alongside a fantastic team of experts. This experience was truly amazing, not just for the high-level research we conducted, but for the positive impact it has had on my career outlook. I am excited to bring these new insights back to my work and continue contributing to our shared scientific goals. Thank you VALIAS team for this incredible opportunity." Monjurul Hoque who joined us from Teagasc, Ireland.

"Thanks to VALIAS, I had the privilege of connecting with esteemed project partners Prof. Magdalini Krokida and Dr. Sofia Papadaki during my one-month secondment at Prinsus in Athens, Greece. This experience greatly expanded my knowledge in the biological characterization of protein, fat and mineral ash content of Lagocephalus sceleratus, providing insights that will be invaluable in advancing my expertise in pharmacology, especially in the areas of toxicity and safety evaluation." Iva Tzvetanova, Assistant Professor, EUC

"My secondment at PRINSUS has been an incredibly rewarding experience. The opportunity to work closely with a skilled team, experiment with innovative functional ingredients, and develop prototypes from concept to evaluation has significantly strengthened my expertise in product development. I am very grateful for the hospitality, collaboration, and knowledge exchange. This experience has positively shaped my professional path and inspired me for future research." Joncer Naibabo who joined us from Teagasc, Ireland.

"Thanks to VALIAS, I had the great opportunity as a PhD student at EUC to spend a one-month secondment at Prinsus in Athens, Greece. During my time there, I worked on the biological characterization of Fistularia commersonii, enhancing my expertise in instrumental analysis for protein, fat, and mineral ash content." Chrysi Tomouzou, EUC

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Meetings

Mid-Term Meeting of the VALIAS Project

This meeting served as an excellent platform for partners to present results, share knowledge, align on upcoming tasks, and reaffirm their commitment to the project's ambitious goals.

Valorization of Invasive Alien Species for Sustainable Food and Feed Applications

During the meeting, partners presented the progress made across all Work Packages, highlighting major achievements

- Identification, listing, and prioritization of Invasive Alien Species (IAS) based on their ecological impact and potential for valorization.
- Green extraction of high-value compounds from prioritized marine IAS such as *Fistularia commersonii*, *Lagocephalus sceleratus*, *Pterois miles*, *Sargassum*, *Asparagopsis*.
- Formulation and encapsulation of bioactive ingredients for food and feed applications
- Toxicological and regulatory evaluation to ensure safety and compliance
- LCA and LCC analysis for assessing environmental and economic sustainability

A big thanks to all partners and secondees for their excellent work and collaboration so far. We look forward to an impactful second half of the project!

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Work progress

In Media

The VALIAS Project has been prominently featured on the Greek news platform **Citygen.gr**, highlighting the project's innovative approach to addressing marine ecological challenges. The full coverage can be accessed via the official Citygen website: <https://citygen.gr/12892/green-business/valias>

GREEN BUSINESS 2 Mins Read

VALIAS: Όταν η απειλή γίνεται ευκαιρία για οικονομική άνθιση - Καινοτομία από τα βάθη της θάλασσας

Valias official **promotional video!**

VALIAS has officially released its primary promotional video offering a comprehensive overview of its pioneering efforts to address the ecological crisis of Invasive Alien Species. Watch the promotional video here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vpExN6dk-wU>

The VALIAS Project on **SKAI TV's EcoNews!**

VALIAS promotes environmental protection by transforming these species into raw materials for the food, cosmetics, and nutraceutical industries. We are turning an environmental challenge into a sustainable opportunity. Watch the full presentation here: https://youtu.be/Y3p_Zs_oLG8

VALIAS Project interview on **CNN Greece!**

The VALIAS Project continues to gain significant media attention, with Dr. Paraskevi Karachle of the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research providing expert commentary during a featured interview with CNN Greece. Dr. Karachle offered an in-depth analysis regarding the increasing prevalence of Invasive Alien Species within Greek marine environments. The full interview is available on the official CNN Greece: <https://www.cnn.gr/perivallon/story/485447>

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Conferences

The VALIAS project was presented at the 11th Ecology and Evolutionary Biology Symposium, held in Ankara, Türkiye by Dr. Paraskevi Karachle from the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR)

Dr. Marina Stramarkou from the VALIAS project presented at the 53rd WEFTA 2025 Conference held in Gdańsk, Poland, from 13-17 October 2025, on the theme: "Blue Bio Opportunities for Health and Value"

The Valias Project was presented at EFFoST 2025, held from 17 to 19 November in Porto Portugal by Prof. Brijesh Tiwari from TEAGASC

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VALIAS Project at European Researchers' Night 2025

EUROPEAN RESEARCHERS' NIGHT

The VALIAS project was once again presented in the European Researchers' Night, hosted in Athens, Greece, on September 26th. The VALIAS mission was showcased with remarkable success, drawing a continuous stream of visitors eager to explore our latest results. The booth served as a dynamic hub for dialogue, where the team demonstrated how marine invasive alien species (traditionally viewed as a biodiversity threat) are being strategically valorized to protect our seas. By transforming these ecological challenges into sustainable opportunities, the project highlighted a clear path toward ecosystem resilience

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Work progress

Bodrum Balik Festival 2025

The Valias team participated in the vibrant Bodrum Balik Festival 2025, held at Club Marma Hotel in Akyarlar, Bodrum where visitors enjoyed lionfish cleaning demonstrations, cooking and tasting sessions, boat trips, and Greek & Turkish cultural performances.

There were over 60 stands featuring marine-inspired crafts and 20 food stalls serving local seafood and invasive fish tastings. The festival highlighted the importance of awareness and innovation in utilizing marine resources responsibly.

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2nd VALIAS WORKSHOP - VALORIZATION OF MARINE IVASIVE ALIEN SPECIES A PATHWAY TOWARDS THE PROTECTION OF EUROPEAN MARINE BIODIVERSITY

The 2st Workshop of the VALIAS Project was part of the broader event “Innovating for a Sustainable Food Future: Bridging Research, Industry and Consumers”, featuring EU-funded projects like EXCEL4PRO, FRIETS and HECOF successfully held on June 26th at the Multimedia Amphitheatre, NTUA Library in Athens. The event brought together changemakers in marine sustainability, circular economy and innovative product development.

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Work progress

Events

Engaging with the AZTI Summer School 2025, Valias Project participation focused on the intersection of Artificial Intelligence and Citizen Science, specifically exploring their roles in the advanced monitoring and assessment of marine ecosystems

AZTI Summer School held in San Sebastián from 3 to 5 June 2025, organized by AZTI and supported by projects like ANERIS, BioBoost+, GuardIAS, and others, this 21st edition focused on cutting-edge tools for ocean monitoring

VALIAS (MSCA Horizon Europe, grant agreement 101131441) is transforming invasive marine species into sustainable ingredients for food, aquafeed, and cosmetics.

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Consumer Events

Valias Project was desiminated by our partners from NUEVO at VIV Asia 2025 in Bangkok, Thailand, from 12 to 14 March 2025.

The VALIAS Project was represented by Savvas Dimitriadis our partner from NUEVO, at the Middle East Poultry Expo 2025 held in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, from 14 to 16 April 2025.

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Achievements

WP3: Marine Invasive Alien Species' Selection and Data Collection for Mapping

In 2025, the VALIAS consortium successfully compiled and validated a comprehensive list of target marine invasive alien species (IAS), including *Asparagopsis armata*, *Sargassum* spp., *Crepidula fornicata*, *Lagocephalus sceleratus*, *Siganus* spp., *Fistularia commersonii*, and *Diadema setosum*. Extensive data collection activities were carried out to map their geographical distribution, abundance, biological characteristics, and ecological impact across the Mediterranean and Atlantic regions. Furthermore, key information regarding their potential applications in the food, feed, and cosmetic industries was gathered, providing a strong scientific basis for subsequent valorization strategies.

WP4: Recovery and Formulation of Valuable Compounds - Toxicity and Safety Evaluation

Significant progress was achieved in optimizing green extraction technologies for the recovery of high-purity bioactive compounds from selected IAS. The project investigated innovative encapsulation strategies based on protein and polysaccharide matrices derived from IAS biomass, aiming to enhance compound stability and bioavailability. In parallel, preliminary toxicity and safety evaluations were initiated to ensure the suitability of the extracted and formulated compounds for use in food, feed, and cosmetic applications.

WP5: Development of Final Products of Commercial Interest

During 2025, close collaboration between academic institutions and industrial partners enabled the identification of promising product concepts in the areas of functional foods, aquafeed, and cosmetic formulations enriched with IAS-derived bioactive compounds. Initial feasibility and stability studies were performed, alongside market-oriented discussions to assess consumer acceptance and regulatory considerations. These activities laid the groundwork for the development of innovative, safe, and sustainable products aligned with growing market demand for natural bio-based ingredients.

WP6: Sustainability Assessment - Economic Evaluation of Valorization Pathways

Preliminary datasets were selected and structured to conduct Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) studies evaluating the environmental performance of the valorization pathways developed within VALIAS. These analyses focused on assessing eco-efficiency and identifying opportunities to reduce environmental impacts while enhancing economic value creation. The results will support evidence-based optimization of processing routes and guide strategic decisions toward sustainable industrial implementation.

Find more about us on social media

 X: VALIASProject

 Facebook: Valias

 Linked In: VALIAS project

and on our website

<https://valias.eu/>

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